

CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF ILEOCECAL REFLUX DISEASE IN CHILDREN WITH NONDIFFERENTIATED CONNECTIVE TISSUE DYSPLASIA

M.K. Sharipova

Department of Faculty Pediatrics, Tashkent State Medical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18083549>

Abstract. *This study presents the results of examining ileocecal reflux disease (ICRD) in children with underlying nondifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia (CTD). Children in the primary group demonstrated more pronounced and prolonged abdominal pain in the right iliac region, accompanied by phenotypic signs of CTD. Inflammatory changes were detected in both upper and lower gastrointestinal tract segments. ICRD was frequently associated with various developmental anomalies and persistent recurrent abdominal syndrome.*

Keywords: *non-differentiated connective tissue dysplasia; children; ileocecal reflux disease.*

Introduction. Non-differentiated CTD represents a heterogeneous group of hereditary disorders, the pathogenic basis of which is determined by individual genomic characteristics; clinical manifestation is often triggered by environmental factors. CTD serves as a foundation for the development of various chronic diseases affecting multiple organs and systems. The gastrointestinal tract is particularly susceptible to involvement in CTD, with digestive pathology observed in over 70% of cases. CTD is often accompanied by changes in the size and length of gastrointestinal organs, such as megacolon and dolichosigma, which can significantly affect organ function. Hypomotor disorders of the gastrointestinal tract are also frequently observed. Motor-tonic dysfunction, sphincter weakness, and subsequent reflux are commonly associated with clinical gastrointestinal symptoms in CTD patients.

Causes of reflux include valve or sphincter insufficiency due to weakened connective tissue structures and altered pressure gradients within hollow organs. Dysplasia of the upper gastrointestinal tract occurs in 3.8% of cases and the colon in 40.2%, often accompanied by functional disorders. One manifestation of CTD is primary insufficiency of the Bauhin valve, contributing to small intestine contamination. Patients with primary insufficiency of the Bauhin valve often exhibit multiple stigmata of connective tissue dysmorphogenesis. However, the specific course of ICRD in the context of CTD in children remains insufficiently studied.

Despite its prevalence, the clinical characteristics of ICRD in children with phenotypic signs of CTD are poorly understood, which determined the aim of this study.

Objective

To identify the clinical features of ileocecal reflux disease in children with phenotypic signs of nondifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia.

Materials and Methods. A total of 65 children aged 6–14 years with ICRD were examined at City Children’s Clinical Hospital No. 4. Patients were divided into two groups:

- Primary group — 43 children with CTD signs (phenotypic score >4)
- Comparison group — 22 children without CTD signs

All children underwent clinical and anamnesis evaluation, including structured interviews regarding patient complaints, their characteristics and duration, and common CTD phenotypic signs. Laboratory and instrumental studies included abdominal ultrasound, gastroduodenoscopy, and barium enema (irrigography).

Inclusion criteria: clinical and instrumental confirmation of ileocecal reflux. CTD phenotypic assessment included posture, body type, chest deformities, joint hypermobility, and craniofacial and skeletal anomalies.

Results and Discussion. All children in the primary group exhibited more than 4 CTD phenotypic signs. The most frequent included thin translucent skin, scoliotic posture, funnel chest, flat feet, and slender hands. Asthenic body type and reduced nutrition combined with muscle hypotonia were common. Facial dysmorphias included ear lobe deformations and malocclusion. Other features included fifth finger deviations, sandal gaps, and disproportionate toe length. Highly specific CTD markers were not identified in children with ICRD, aligning with previous findings on the absence of universal phenotypic mechanisms in CTD.

Clinically, the dominant symptom in the primary group was abdominal pain (95%) compared to 77% in the comparison group ($p > 0.0032$), mainly in the right iliac region and/or right periumbilical area, unrelated to food intake. Pain was chronic. Palpation revealed maximal tenderness in the right iliac area in the primary group. Appetite reduction was significantly more frequent. Dyspeptic symptoms such as nausea and vomiting were observed without significant group differences. Constipation and asthenic complaints, such as fatigue and irritability, were more frequent in the primary group.

Ultrasound revealed liver and pancreas changes, including enhanced vascular patterns and organ enlargement; echostructural differences between groups were not significant ($p < 0.05$). Gastroduodenoscopy showed predominance of chronic superficial gastroduodenitis with duodeno-gastric reflux in the primary group. *H. pylori* testing was more often positive in the primary group. Irrigography indicated that ileocecal reflux was significantly more often associated with intestinal anomalies (dolichosigma, coloptosis) in children with CTD (59%, $p < 0.05$).

Despite therapy, the primary group had a higher rate of rehospitalization due to recurrent abdominal syndrome — 21% versus 6% in the comparison group ($p < 0.05$).

Clinical Case. Patient B., 10 years old, presented with recurrent right iliac and periumbilical abdominal pain, periodic constipation, decreased appetite, and episodes of nausea for 10–12 months. Pain was unrelated to food intake and worsened with physical activity. Parents reported irritability and fatigue.

History: normal early development, positive family history (mother — mitral valve prolapse, grandmother — varicose veins, sister — spinal deformity). Two prior gastrointestinal infections; frequent URIs and exercise-related abdominal pain.

Examination: asthenic body type, below-average weight. CTD phenotypic features: thin skin, joint hypermobility (Beighton score 7), flat-valgus feet, scoliotic posture, funnel chest, malocclusion, high-arched palate. Abdominal palpation: tenderness along colon and right iliac region, moderate distension, increased peristalsis, no peritoneal irritation.

Instrumental findings: gastroduodenoscopy — superficial gastroduodenitis, duodeno-gastric reflux, mucosal hyperemia; *H. pylori* positive. Irrigography — ileocecal reflux, dolichosigma, coloptosis.

Laboratory: moderate leukocytosis; biochemistry without significant deviations; coprography indicated dysbiosis.

Diagnosis:

ICRD with chronic recurrent course, nondifferentiated CTD, moderate severity, coloptosis, dolichosigma, duodeno-gastric reflux, chronic gastroduodenitis, H. pylori positive.

Treatment:

Anti-H. pylori therapy, prokinetics, antispasmodics, dietary and lifestyle recommendations, orthopedic regimen and physiotherapy, vitamin-mineral supplementation including magnesium, correction of CTD manifestations.

Outcome:

After 3 months — reduced pain, normalized bowel movements, decreased nausea and bloating, persistent but less intense reflux on follow-up irrigography.

Conclusion

Children with ICRD on the background of non-differentiated CTD exhibit more pronounced and prolonged abdominal pain, particularly in the right iliac region, with constipation and asthenic complaints. CTD increases the risk of upper gastrointestinal inflammatory changes, often related to H. pylori infection, and is associated with intestinal developmental anomalies such as dolichosigma and coloptosis. Early detection of CTD phenotypic signs improves diagnosis and prognosis.

REFERENCES

1. Kadurina T.I. Hereditary collagenopathies (clinic, diagnosis, treatment, and follow-up). St. Petersburg: Nevsky Dialect, 2020.
2. Yakovlev V.M., Glotov A.V., Yagoda A.V. Immunological syndromes in hereditary connective tissue dysplasia. Stavropol, 2015.
3. Nechaeva G.I., Lalyukova E.A., Mekina N.A. Gastrointestinal pathology in patients with connective tissue dysplasia // Kazan Medical Journal. — 2007. — Vol.88, No.5 (supplement). — P.76–81.
4. Akhmedov V.A. Reflux disease and target organs. Moscow, 2017.
5. Klemenov A.V. Extracardiac manifestations of nondifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia // Clinical Medicine. — 2015. — No.10. — P.4–7.
6. Klemenov A.V. Bauhin valve insufficiency as a visceral manifestation of nondifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia // Therapeutic Archive. — 2017. — No.4. — P.44–46.
7. Demin V.F., Klyuchnikov S.O., Klyuchnikova M.A. The significance of connective tissue dysplasias in pediatric pathology // Current Pediatrics. — 2015. — Vol.4(1). — P.50–56.
8. Zemtsovsky E.V. Dysplastic phenotypes. Dysplastic heart. St. Petersburg: Olga, 2017.